

Negative Emotions Can Interfere with the Inhibitory Effect of Proactive Control on Implicit Stereotypes

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

In the present study, the gender face pictures were used as priming stimuli, and the weapons recognition paradigm and process separation program were used to explore the influence of emotion and proactive control on implicit gender stereotypes. Study 1 (n=56) explored the processing of proactive control under different conflict levels and its influence on implicit gender stereotypes. The results showed that under high conflict level, the response time was the shortest and the correct rate was the highest. In Study 2 (n=96), emotional variables were added to explore the influence of proactive control on the intervention effect of implicit gender stereotypes under different conflict levels. The results showed that the participants had the longest reaction time and the lowest correct rate among the high conflict levels in negative emotional type. Process dissociation analysis showed that the proactive control mode reflected the change of control processing, rather than the automatic association of stereotypes. These findings showed that the proactive control processing mode appears more in the high conflict level, which helps to weaken the implicit gender stereotype; However, negative emotions can interfere with the proactive control process, and can not optimize cognition, so as to suppress implicit gender stereotypes.

Keywords: EMOTION, PROACTIVE CONTROL, IMPLICIT, GENDER STEREOTYPE

Introduction

Stereotype activation is a cognitive process and an implicit and universal aspect of interpersonal perception (Moskowitz & Stone, 2012). Studies

have shown that stereotype can produce prejudice in many different ways, and it represents a human response that a specific individual may want to control (Moskowitz & Ignarri, 2009). The expression of implicit bias reflects both automatic and controlled processes (Payne, 2001). That is to say, although rigid attitudes may be automatically activated, the response to these stereotypes can be controlled (Mark & Muraven, 2008).

Up to now, almost all the researches on controlling stereotypes or prejudices have focused on reactive control. Reactive control is to resist the influence of stereotype after it is imposed and discovered by consciousness

(Mark & Muraven, 2008). Anti-stereotype sample exposure method (Ramasubramanian, 2015), vivid anti-stereotype scenario story method (Burn et al., 2017), false IAT result feedback (Cvencek et al., 2010) and other methods all belong to the intervention training method of reactive control. Previous studies have shown that these methods can effectively weaken the impact of stereotypes (Lai et al., 2016). However, although reactive control provides an important mechanism for overcoming prejudice, it only comes into play after the emergence or activation of prejudice, so it is easily affected by various situational factors and cognitive resources, thus destroying its effectiveness and diminishing the intervention effect (Lambert et al., 2003; Calvin, 2016) .

Different from reactive control, proactive control is a completely different concept of intervention. As a goal-related control method, it is aimed at a person's expected reaction, not the source of prejudice. Proactive control adopts the method of manipulating task interference, which can effectively transfer the focus of stereotype to the task goal itself before activating the relevant information about stereotype in people's minds, and limit the possibility of implicit bias expression in behavior by experiencing task difficulties or increasing motivation for one's expected behavior (Amodio et al., 2018). Previous studies have shown that the reaction of stereotype bias observed in ethnic classification tasks is mainly driven by conflict, that is, high conflict enhances the attention of participants to task objectives and may lead to proactive control mode (Bartholow & Dickter, 2008; Dickter & Bartholow, 2010). In the above research, control is mainly aimed at racial clues, and in most cases, it is aimed at racial prejudice. However, in real life, people are more susceptible to gender-related stereotypes, especially in the fixed concept of which occupations men and women are more suitable for, which will lead to occupational gender segregation (Gross, 1968), thus negatively affecting employment in different industries (Koenig & Eagly, 2014). Unfortunately, the influence of proactive control on implicit gender stereotypes has not attracted wide attention of researchers. In a recent study (Amodio et al., 2018), researchers used weapon recognition paradigm (Payne, 2001) to investigate the influence of proactive control on implicit racial prejudice and implicit racial stereotype. It was confirmed for the first time that individuals would adopt proactive control processing mode in high interference situations, and showed implicit racial prejudice and implicit racial stereotype more obviously in low interference situations than the baseline group. It remains to be explored whether the cognitive processing mode of proactive control can also effectively suppress implicit gender stereotypes.

Cognitive function and emotion interact in shaping goal-oriented behavior (Pessoa et al., 2011). Essentially, proactive control is a cognitive processing model which needs conflict monitoring and conflict resolution under conflict adaptation conditions and can effectively reduce implicit stereotypes (Gratton et al., 1992). Conflict adaptation is considered as a typical example of human flexible action control (Dreisbach & Fischer, 2015). It is worth noting that conflict stimulation can stimulate the process of emotional deregulation (Dreisbach & Fritz, 2013). Pessoa(2009) put forward the dual processing theory, which holds that the nature of emotions and the emotional type of participants are important factors that affect conflict processing.

Previous studies have shown that negative emotions affect the conflict adaptation process in different types of conflict tasks. For example, in working memory tasks, negative picture stimuli unrelated to tasks interfere with task performance to a greater extent than neutral picture stimuli (Dolcos & McCarthy, 2006). Pessoa et al., (2011) used a Stroop-like task to study the influence of negative emotions on conflict-driven control mechanism. It is found that compared with neutral picture stimulation, task-independent negative picture stimulation significantly reduces conflict-driven control effect (i.e., conflict adaptation). However, in the field of social cognition, there are few researches in this area. Therefore, we try to further explore how emotional type regulates the control process of implicit stereotype driven by conflict. That is to say, whether the negative emotional type will interfere with proactive control, thus affecting implicit gender stereotypes is the focus of our attention.

Based on this, the present study used the methods of controlling conflict level and inducing emotion to explore whether proactive control can inhibit implicit gender stereotypes, and the influence of proactive control on the intervention effect of implicit gender stereotypes in different emotional types. We inferred that: (1) Compared with baseline level, individuals with low conflict level would show more obvious implicit gender stereotypes, but individuals with high conflict level would adopt more proactive control processing mode, and implicit gender stereotypes would be suppressed; (2) Compared with positive emotional type and neutral emotional type, negative emotions would reduce conflict adaptation, that was, at the high level of conflict of negative emotions, negative emotions would interfere with the proactive control process, and could not effectively suppress implicit gender stereotypes.

Study 1

Materials and methods

Participants

Fifty-six participants (26 males and 30 females, with an average age of 22.28 years and a standard deviation of ± 2.30 years) participated in this experiment. All the participants had normal vision or corrected vision and were proficient in computer operation, and had never participated in similar experiments before. All participants signed the informed consent form, and received corresponding remuneration after the experiment.

Materials

Stimulus were adapted from Payne(2001). Two male and two female face images were used as priming stimuli. These pictures were selected from the Chinese facial emotion picture system, all of which are 5.3cm \times 4cm in size. The purpose of selecting the pen was that it looked similar to the syringe and was a neutral irritant. The target stimulus consisted of four pictures of syringes and four pictures of pens, each of which was the same size as the priming stimulus.

Design

A 3 (conflict level: high conflict/low conflict/baseline) \times 2 (priming stimulus: male face/female face) \times 2

(target stimulus: syringe/pen) within design were carried out. Dependent variables were the average reaction time (ms) and accuracy rate (%) of classification tasks. There were 6 blocks in the experiment, each block had 40 trials and 240 trials in total.

Conflict handling was accomplished by changing the matching ratio of consistent tasks in one trial (Amodio et al., 2018). The high conflict level included 80% stereotype inconsistent attempts (male-pen, female-pen) and 20% stereotype consistent attempts (male-pen, female-syringe). The distribution ratio of consistent and inconsistent trials in baseline level was 50%. The low conflict level includes 20% inconsistent attempts and 80% consistent attempts.

Procedures

Priming task: adapted from Payne(2001). The experimenter told the participants that they needed to complete a computerized task. The experimenter explained that the task was to test speed and accuracy, and told the participants that they would see several groups of pictures flashed quickly on the display. They needed to ignore the first picture, because the first one was always a gender face, which would send out a target stimulus signal to prompt them to respond to the second picture. The participants were asked to press one of the two keys to classify each target as a syringe or a pen. Before the start of the formal experiment, the participants received a short practice experiment to familiarize themselves with the targets and to quickly classify them. The stimulus of all practice experiments was different from that of formal experiments.

Once entering the formal experiment, each trial started with a fixation point "+", followed by a male face picture or a female face picture (priming stimulus), and then a syringe picture or a pen picture (target stimulus). The priming stimulus was replaced by the target stimulus immediately after it stayed on the screen for 200 ms. The target stimulus was replaced by a mask stimulus 200ms later. Mask stimulus was always presented on the screen until the participants responded. Then, the latency from the start of target stimulation to the nearest millisecond was recorded. For each trial, the next priming stimulus occurs 500ms after the previous reaction. Priming-target stimulus pairs were presented by a computer program in random order. The specific trial process is as follows (see Fig 1).

Figure 1. Example of consistent trial flowchart

Results

Behavior result analysis

The data processing method adopts the method used by Amodio et al.(2018) in his research. We only screened the data of the participants whose reaction time was between 200 ms and 1200 ms, and the accuracy rate in this reaction time interval.

A 3 (emotion type) × 3 (conflict level) × 2 (priming stimulus) × 2 (target stimulus) repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that the main response time effect of conflict level was very significant, $F(1, 11) = 18.537, p < 0.001, \eta^2=0.055$. The correct rate of conflict level was very significant, $F(2, 11) = 17.740, p < 0.001, \eta^2 = 0.053$. The interaction between conflict level and response time of priming stimulus was significant, $F(2, 11) = 5.889, p= 0.003, \eta^2 = 0.018$, which was not significant under other conditions.

Post comparison showed that the response time of high conflict level ($M_{high\ conflict} = 482.150, SD = 15.023$) was significantly different from that of baseline level ($M_{baseline} = 436.997, SD = 14.676$), $t(53) = 1.68, p=0.032$; The reaction time of high conflict level ($M_{high\ conflict} = 482.150, SD = 15.023$) was significantly different from that of low conflict level ($M_{low\ conflict} = 355.788, SD=14.777$), $t(53)=3.34, p <0.001$. There was a significant difference in response time between baseline ($M_{baseline} = 436.99, SD = 14.6$) and low conflict level ($M_{low\ conflict} = 355.788, SD = 14.777$), $t(53) = 1.60, p < 0.001$. The accuracy of high conflict level ($M_{high\ conflict} = 0.934, SD = 0.005$) was significantly different from that of baseline level ($M_{baseline} = 0.959, SD = 0.005$), $t(53) = 0.99, p < 0.001$, while the accuracy rate of high conflict level ($M_{high\ conflict} = 0.934, SD = 0.005$) and low conflict level ($M_{low\ conflict} = 0.977, SD = 0.005$) had significant difference, $t(53) = 0.99, p < 0.001$ (see Table 1).

Table 1. Mean value of response time and accuracy under different conflict levels (N = 56)

	High conflict $M(SD)$	Baseline $M(SD)$	Low conflict $M(SD)$
Response time (ms)	482.15(15.023)	436.997 (14.676)	355.788 (14.777)
Accuracy (%)	0.934 (0.005)	0.959 (0.005)	0.977 (0.005)

Among them, the interaction between conflict level and response time of priming stimulus was significant, $F(2,11) = 5.889$, $p = 0.003$, $\eta^2 = 0.018$. The results showed that the response time of high conflict level ($M_{high\ conflict} = 477.603$, $SD = 20.970$) and low conflict level ($M_{low\ conflict} = 347.292$, $SD = 20.873$) were significantly different under the priming stimulus of male faces, $t(50) = 4.893$, $p < 0.001$; There was a significant difference in response time between baseline ($M_{baseline} = 492.270$, $SD = 20.777$) and low conflict level ($M_{low\ conflict} = 347.292$, $SD = 20.873$), $t(50) = 1.68$, $p < 0.001$; Under the priming stimulation of female faces, the response time of high conflict level ($M_{high\ conflict} = 484.624$, $SD = 21.069$) and baseline level ($M_{baseline} = 381.242$, $SD = 20.682$) had significant difference, $t(50) = 4.136$, $p < 0.001$; There was a significant difference between high conflict level ($M_{high\ conflict} = 484.624$, $SD = 21.069$) and low conflict level ($M_{low\ conflict} = 364.283$, $SD = 20.873$), $t(50) = 3.643$, $p < 0.001$ (see Fig 2).

Figure 2. Response time under different priming stimuli and different conflict levels

Process dissociation analysis

Cognitive control refers to the ability to detect and resolve conflict response trends by switching from automatic response mode to controlled response mode when dependent on the environment, so that human beings can consciously perform appropriate but weak responses when facing inappropriate but beneficial reactions (Pastötter et al., 2013). We used the Process Dissociation Program (PDP) further tested our prediction, that is, the interference of our manipulation tasks (proactive control) will mainly affect controlled processing, rather than automatic processing (Payne, 2001). PDP is a method to evaluate control processing and automatic processing from behavioral patterns. In the PDP framework, control estimation (PDP-C) indicates the probability that a person will respond in an accurate and consistent way without stereotype-driven bias caused by racial priming stimulus (P [correct response to consistency test]– P [wrong response to inconsistency test]) caused by race priming stimulus. Automatic Assessment (PDP-A) indicates that, in the case of control failure, a person's response will be affected by prejudice of race priming stimulus due to its association with stereotype of target stimulus (Payne, 2001). Although PDP-C is not a purely proactive control indicator, it may also reflect the degree of reactive control, but it provides evidence about the control process.

In this study, we numbered the accuracy rates of different priming stimuli and different target stimuli. Among them, the accuracy rate of the trial under the matching of male face and pen is A, the accuracy rate of the trial under the matching of male face and syringe is B, the accuracy rate of the trial under the matching of female face and syringe is C, and the accuracy rate of the trial under the matching of female face and pen is D.

Then the calculation formula of proactive control (hereinafter referred to as McontH) of male face priming stimulus under high conflict, baseline and low conflict level is shown in formula (1):

$$McontH=A-(1-B) \quad (1)$$

The calculation formula of reactive control (hereinafter referred to as MautoH) of male face priming stimulus under high conflict, baseline and low conflict level is shown in formula (2):

$$MautoH=\frac{1-B}{1-McontH} \quad (2)$$

The calculation formula of proactive control (hereinafter referred to as FautoH) of female face priming stimulus under high conflict, baseline and low conflict level is shown in formula (3):

$$FcontH=C-(1-D) \quad (3)$$

The calculation formula of reactive control estimation value (hereinafter referred to as FautoH) of female face priming stimulus under high conflict, baseline and low conflict level is shown in formula (4):

$$FautoH=\frac{1-D}{1-FcontH} \quad (4)$$

The results of one-way ANOVA showed that the main effect of proactive control estimation of conflict level was significant, $F(2, 323) = 4934.31, p < 0.001$, and the main effect of reactive control of conflict level was significant, $F(2, 323) = 4824.35, p < 0.001$. This effect shows that the high conflict level ($M = 0.940, SD = 0.089$) has the highest degree of proactive control, the low level of conflict ($M = 0.011, SD = 0.054$) has the lowest degree of proactive control, $t(53) = 92.2, p < 0.001$, while the baseline level ($M = 0.004, SD = 0.090$) has the moderate degree of proactive control.

The difference of reactive control between high conflict level ($M = -0.004, SD = 0.111$) and baseline level ($M = 0.963, SD = 0.062$) was very significant, $t(53) = -79.23, p < 0.001$, while the difference between high conflict level ($M = -0.004, SD = 0.111$) and low conflict level ($M = 0.026, SD = 0.067$) was significant, $t(53) = -2.32, p = 0.01$ (see Table 2).

Table 2. Estimated value *M* (*SD*) of proactive control and reactive control under different conflict levels

	Proactive control <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	Reactive control <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)
High conflict	0.940(0.089)	-0.004(0.111)
Baseline	0.004(0.090)	0.963(0.062)
Low conflict	0.011(0.054)	0.026(0.067)

Discussion

In Study 1, the task interference was used to perform the task of image recognition and classification, and the processing of proactive control under different conflict levels and its influence on implicit gender stereotypes were investigated.

The correct rate at high conflict level is significantly higher than that at low conflict level and baseline level. The response time at high conflict level was significantly lower than that at low conflict level and baseline level. Under the priming stimulus of male face, the difference of reaction time between high conflict level and low conflict level is very significant; Under the stimulation of female faces, there is a significant difference in response time between high and low conflict levels. This result shows that although the subjects with high conflict are affected by priming stimulus, the subjects experience higher difficulty because of the high proportion of inconsistent attempts at high conflict level, so they use more proactive control processing modes that consume cognitive resources for cognitive regulation and conflict monitoring, which helps to weaken implicit impression (Amodio et al., 2018). On the contrary, under low conflict and baseline level, the subjects are more susceptible to reaction control driven by priming stimulus, which makes them more susceptible to implicit gender stereotypes in this process. This is consistent with the previous research results. The basic discovery in the classical interference task is that the interference caused by reaction conflict in one experiment will be greatly reduced in subsequent experiments, even if it is not eliminated (Dreisbach & Fischer, 2015).

Processing separation analysis confirmed that these results represent the change of control processing, rather than the activation of stereotype association or the change of operability. It is consistent with the previous evidence, that is, high conflict environment will lead to an proactive control mode (Gratton et al., 1992). Comparing the estimated values of PDP processing model, it is found that the control processing under high conflict condition is stronger than that under low conflict condition. When the subjects encounter high conflict, they need proactive control, which helps to enhance the goal-oriented response. In contrast, the exaggerated prejudice pattern observed under the condition of low conflict is consistent with the greater dependence on reaction control, and reaction control will be carried out only when there is reaction conflict. As we can see, reaction control is more likely to fail than proactive control. This model is further consistent

with the idea that proactive control and reactive control provide complementary functions according to the needs of scenarios.

Study 2

Materials and methods

Participants

The research was approved by the Science and Research Ethics Committee of the School of Psychology of Northwest Normal University. Ninety-six participants (56 women and 40 men) participated in the experiment and received corresponding remuneration after the experiment. All participants signed informed consent forms.

Materials

The experimental materials for priming the task are the same as Study 1. We choosed to induce emotions by presenting emotional movie clips, because this is one of the most reliable and widely used methods in experimental emotional manipulation (Rottenberg et al., 2007) .There were three kinds of stimuli to induce different emotions: " Bohu Tang points Xiang Qiu" was used as a stimulus to induce positive emotions; The documentary Nanjing Nightmare was used as a stimulus to induce negative emotions. Animal documentaries were used as stimuli to induce neutral emotions. In order to prevent the participants from guessing the real purpose of short films and triggering the process of emotion regulation (Rottenberg et al., 2007), they were told in advance that they would participate in two short and irrelevant studies: the first study was watching short films and then answering questions about movies; The second was the reaction time experiment on digital processing.

Design

A 3 (emotion: positive/neutral/negative) ×3 (conflict level: high conflict/low conflict/baseline) ×2 (priming stimulus: male face/female face) ×2 (target stimulus: syringe/pen) mixture design was carried out. Among them, conflict level, priming stimulus and target stimulus were between participant variables, and emotion was within participant variable. The dependent variables were the average reaction time (ms) and the accuracy rate (%) of classification tasks. Treatment of conflict level is the same as Study 1.

Procedures

Emotion measurement: First, the participants completed a questionnaire survey. The PANAS scale (Watson et al. 1988) includes positive emotional self-rating and negative emotional self-rating, aiming at measuring the current emotional type of the participants. The measurement used a 5-point Likert reaction score ranging from 1 (almost none) to 5 (very many). Next, the participants randomly watched videos inducing different emotions, and immediately filled out the PANAS after watching. At the end of the formal experiment, the participants completed the PANAS for the last time. The priming task is the same as Study 1.

Results

Emotional evoked analysis

In this study, paired sample T-test was used to process the data of pre-test, post-test and final test (see Table 3). As expected, the emotion induction of the three groups was obviously successful. There was a significant difference between pre-test($M=2.866$, $SD=0.705$) and post-test($M=2.382$, $SD=0.941$) in the induction of positive emotions in neutral group ($n=32$), $t(33)=3.551$, $p=0.001$, and the difference between the pre-test ($M=1.556$, $SD=0.591$) and post-test($M=1.435$, $SD=0.496$) of negative emotions in the neutral group was not significant, $t(31)=1.11$, $p=0.275$. The difference between pre-test ($M=2.622$, $SD=0.446$) and post-test($M=3.625$, $SD=0.638$) of positive emotion induction in positive group was very significant ($n=33$), $t(32)=-7.997$, $p<0.001$; In the negative group, the difference between pre-test($M=1.886$, $SD=0.613$) and post-test ($M=3.049$, $SD=0.931$) in inducing negative emotions ($n=31$) was very significant, $t(30)=-7.889$, $p<0.001$.

Table 3. Comparison of pre-test, post-test and final-test in different emotional type groups.

		Pre-test $M(SD)$	Post-test $M(SD)$	Final-test $M(SD)$
Neutral group	Positive emotion	2.866 (0.705)	2.382 (0.941)	2.062 (0.888)
	Negative emotion	1.565 (0.591)	1.435 (0.496)	1.265 (0.308)
Positive group	Positive emotion	2.622 (0.446)	3.625 (0.638)	2.064 (0.838)
	Negative emotion	1.575 (0.596)	1.264 (0.507)	1.365 (0.516)
Negative group	Positive emotion	3.137 (0.873)	1.301 (0.529)	2.389 (0.978)
	Negative emotion	1.886 (0.613)	3.049 (0.931)	1.373 (0.417)

Behavior result analysis

A 3 (emotion type) \times 3 (conflict level) \times 2 (priming stimulus) \times 2(target stimulus) repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) showed that the main effect of reaction time of emotion type was not significant, $F(2,35)= 1.61$, $p=0.2$, $\eta^2 = 0.003$, and the main effect of accuracy rate of emotion type was significant, $F(2,35)= 17.884$, $p<0.001$, $\eta^2=0.032$. The main effect of reaction time at conflict level was significant, $F(2,35)=15.87$, $p<0.001$, $\eta^2=0.028$. The main effect of the accuracy rate of conflict level was significant, $F(2, 35)=13.291$, $p<0.001$, $\eta^2=0.024$. Reaction-time interaction between emotion type and conflict level was significant, $F(4,35)=3.812$, $p=0.004$, $\eta^2=0.014$; The interaction between emotion type, conflict level and reaction time of target stimulation was significant, $F(4, 35)=2.504$, $p=0.041$, $\eta^2=0.009$.

Post comparison showed that the accuracy rate at high conflict level ($M_{high\ conflict}=0.920, SD=0.005$) was significantly lower than that at low conflict level ($M_{low\ conflict}=0.955, SD=0.005$), $t(93)=-4.90, p=0.001$ (see Table 4).

Table 4. Accuracy under different conflict levels (N = 96)

	High conflict $M(SD)$	Baseline $M(SD)$	Low conflict $M(SD)$
Accuracy (%)	0.920(0.005)	0.944(0.005)	0.955 (0.005)

Post comparison showed that the accuracy rate of neutral emotional condition ($M_{neutral}= 0.960, SD=0.073$) was significantly higher than that of negative emotional level ($M_{negative}=0.918, SD=0.114$), $t(93)=5.81, p<0.001$. The difference between the accuracy rate of negative emotional level ($M_{negative}=0.918, SD=0.114$) and that of positive emotional level ($M_{positive}=0.942, SD=0.097$) was very significant, $t(93)=-2.96, p<0.001$ (see Table 5).

Table 5. Accuracy under different emotion types (N = 96)

	Neutral $M(SD)$	Negative $M(SD)$	Positive $M(SD)$
Accuracy (%)	0.960(0.073)	0.918(0.114)	0.942(0.097)

Among them, the reaction time interaction between emotion type and conflict level was significant. We have conducted a simple effect analysis on it. The results showed that under high conflict conditions, the difference between neutral emotion ($M_{neutral}=435.692, SD=17.927$) and negative emotion ($M_{negative}=498.790, SD=16.597$) was significant, $t(93)=2.35, p=0.029$. The difference between neutral emotion ($M_{neutral}=435.692, SD=17.927$) and positive emotion ($M_{positive}=437.353, SD=16.094$) was significant, $t(93)=2.41, p=0.024$; Under baseline conditions, the difference between neutral emotion ($M_{neutral}=455.714, SD=17.373$) and negative emotion ($M_{negative}=391.735, SD=16.532$) was significant, $t(93)=-2.56, p=0.023$ (see Fig 3).

Figure 3. Reaction time at different emotional types and conflict levels

Process dissociation analysis

A 3 (mood type) × 3 (conflict level) repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) shows that the main effect of the proactive control estimate at conflict level was significant, $F(2,8)= 86.009, p<0.001, \eta^2=0.276$. The main effect of the reaction control estimate at conflict level was very significant, $F(2,8)= 92.05, p<0.001, \eta^2=0.289$.

Post comparison showed that there was a significant difference between the high conflict level proactive control estimate ($M_{high\ conflict}=0.880, SD=0.034$) and the low conflict level proactive control estimate ($M_{low\ conflict}=0.370, SD=0.029$), $t(93)=-14.235, p<0.001$. The difference between baseline level proactive control estimate ($M_{baseline}=0.352, SD=0.030$) and low conflict level proactive control estimate ($M_{low\ conflict}=0.370, SD=0.029$) was significant, $t(93)=-14.034, p<0.001$. The difference between the low conflict level reactive control estimate ($M_{low\ conflict}=-0.196, SD=0.047$) and the baseline level reactive control estimate ($M_{baseline}=0.717, SD=0.048$) was very significant, $t(93)=-12.50, p<0.001$. The difference between the low conflict level reactive control estimate ($M_{low\ conflict}=-0.196, SD=0.047$) and the high conflict level reactive control estimate ($M_{high\ conflict}=0.300, SD=0.054$) was very significant, $t(93)=-6.64, p<0.001$. The difference between high conflict level reactive control estimate ($M_{high\ conflict}=0.300, SD=0.054$) and baseline level reactive control estimate ($M_{baseline}=0.717, SD=0.048$) was very significant, $t(93)=-9.03, p<0.001$ (see Fig 4).

Figure 4. Estimation of proactive control and reactive control under different conflict levels

Discussion

The purpose of Study 2 was to explore the influence of proactive control on the intervention effect of implicit gender stereotypes under different emotional types. The results showed that the correct rate under negative emotions was significantly lower than that under neutral and positive conditions. This was consistent with the previous research results. Negative emotional type would interfere with the proactive control process of subjects, and could not effectively suppress stereotypes. We compared the reaction time of different conflict levels in neutral, negative and positive emotional types. The results showed that the reaction time in negative emotional type was significantly higher than that in neutral and positive emotional type under high conflict conditions. This result is consistent with our research hypothesis, which showed that the subjects may consume or occupy more time and cognitive resources for conflict adaptation and emotional regulation in negative emotional type. It may also inhibit conflict adaptation by raising awareness (Van Steenbergen et al., 2010; Kanske et al., 2010; Schuch et al., 2015). This helped to explain the result that the response time of subjects was prolonged under negative emotional conditions (Schuch et al., 2015).

The estimated value of proactive control under high conflict level was significantly higher than that under low conflict and baseline level, which was consistent with the results of Study 1 and previous studies (Amodio et al., 2018). This showed that the participants use the proactive control processing mode more in the cognitive processing under the high conflict level.

Conclusion

The essence of proactive control is a cognitive processing model that exists in conflict processing and needs conflict monitoring and conflict resolution. Compared with reactive control, it has a better intervention effect on implicit racial stereotypes and can play a more inhibitory role. Previous studies have shown that task-independent negative emotional stimulation can reduce the effect of conflict-driven control (Pessoa et al., 2011). However, as far as this relationship is concerned, it is rare to study whether negative emotional type interferes with proactive control, thus affecting implicit gender stereotypes. According to the research on the interaction between cognition and emotion (e.g., Pessoa, 2010; Dreisbach & Fritz, 2013), proactive control model (Amodio et al., 2018), and literature that negative emotions affect conflict-driven executive control (e.g., Pessoa et al., 2011). In Study 1, we used the method of controlling conflict level to verify whether proactive control can inhibit implicit gender stereotypes. In the second experiment, the influence of proactive control on the intervention effect of implicit stereotypes in different emotional types was discussed by controlling conflict level and inducing emotions. Compared with the baseline group, the low conflict group showed more obvious implicit gender stereotypes, but the high conflict group would adopt more proactive control processing mode, and the implicit gender stereotypes would be suppressed compared with positive emotional type and neutral emotional type, negative emotion would reduce conflict adaptation, that was, at the high conflict level of negative emotion, negative emotion would interfere with the proactive control process, and could not effectively suppress implicit gender stereotypes.

In the two studies, we proved that, compared with the low conflict level, the processing mode of proactive control was more likely to appear under the high conflict level, thus effectively suppressing the implicit gender stereotype. The results of processing separation program showed that the estimated value of proactive control under high conflict level was significantly higher than that under low conflict and baseline level, which was consistent with previous studies (Gratton et al., 1992; Amodio et al., 2018). Studies have shown that conflict is considered as a catalyst to trigger cognitive control, so as to prevent interference with subsequent experiments in tasks (Goschke & Dreisbach, 2008). Under the high level of conflict, because of the high proportion of inconsistent attempts, the participants experienced more difficult tasks, thus using more proactive control processing modes that needed to consume cognitive resources for cognitive regulation and conflict monitoring. This processing mode pointed to a goal-oriented behavior, which helped to suppress distractions and weaken implicit gender stereotypes (Mayr et al., 2003). It can be seen that these results represent changes in control processing, not changes in activation or operability of stereotype association.

We compared the reaction time at different conflict levels in three emotional types. The results showed that the reaction time at high conflict level was significantly higher in negative emotional type than in neutral and positive emotional type. This result was consistent with our research hypothesis and Pessoa et al.(2011). Negative emotions would interfere with proactive control, resulting in slower response and lower accuracy rate. First of all, Schuch(2015) shows that negative emotions have an impact on the setting of speed-accuracy trade-off, and when the interference is the greatest, negative emotions are more cautious. Secondly, according to the dual competition model (Pessoa, 2009), task performance is usually impaired when emotional stimuli unrelated to tasks exist, because at least part of the resources required by the main tasks are used to deal with emotional stimuli. For example, when a negative picture unrelated to the task appears before an inconsistent test in a Stroop-like task, the interference effect of increased reaction time is reported (Hart et al., 2010). In addition, the conflict monitoring model (Botvinick et al., 2001) proposes that the conflict-driven control adjustment occurs because the top-down attention mechanism is triggered after the conflict is detected. These adjustment mechanisms will apply top-down control in subsequent experiments, thus reducing interference. Finally, conflict stimuli have inherent aversion (Dreisbach & Fritz, 2013), and the aversion signals presented between conflict experiments will eliminate conflict adaptation because they utilize resources that are no longer available for adaptation (Pessoa et al., 2011). According to the above research and theoretical model, a potential explanation for our experimental results was that the resources needed for conflict processing were shared or transferred by the processing of negative emotional stimulation, so the conflict adaptation effect was suppressed, the interference to cognitive processing was increased, and the control of subsequent experiments was poor.

Although the participants were more likely to have proactive control processing mode at high conflict level, and the negative emotional type would affect this process. However, there were still some shortcomings in this study. Studies have shown that young adults are more inclined to take proactive control than children or

adolescents (Andrews-Hanna et al., 2011); However, aging has a great influence on proactive control (Czernocowski et al., 2010). We speculated that in the field of social cognition, the influence of proactive control on the intervention effect of implicit stereotype varied with age, which needed to be confirmed and developed in further research.

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